

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style and guidelines:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or with small-scale studies in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row)
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha; not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out in full the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were . . . or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in . . .
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals, 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or some numbers higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names (or commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment).
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should have quantified data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.)

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Performance of IR36 in Bihar, India

R. C. Chaudhary, S. Saran, and V. N. Sahai, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna 800001, India

IR36, an early-maturing, high yielding variety, was introduced in Bihar in an IRTTP nursery (IRYN-E) in 1977 kharif. From 1977 to 1982 it yielded an average 3.3 t/ha in wet season, while check variety Ratna yielded 2.7 t/ha (Table 1). In the adaptive research farm test during 1981 wet season, IR36 yielded higher than check CR44-35 at four locations (Table 2). In 1979 and 1982 dry seasons, it performed satisfactorily (Table 3).

IR36 matures in 115-120 days and has

Table 1. Average yield of IR36 at six sites in Bihar, 1977-82 wet season.

Location	Yield (t/ha)		%increase over the check
	IR36	Ratna (check)	
Patna	3.3	2.5	29.2
Pusa	2.9	3.0	-2.8
Kanke	2.6	2.3	10.6
Sabour	2.4	2.8	-14.5
Telaundha	2.9	2.4	23.5
Dhangain	5.3	5.6	6.0

Preparation of *Oryza pollen* grains for scanning electron microscope analysis

Xue-Bin Xu (Hsae-Pin Hsu), IRRI; Li-Qing He and Hui-zhen Han, South China Agricultural College, Guangzhou, China; and B. S. Vergara, IRRI

The morphological features of the pollen grains of different species in the genus *Oryza* are almost uniform. The grains are usually spheroid or ovoid with a single aperture that has a conspicuous operculum at or near its center. Descriptions of rice pollen grain surfaces vary and can be studied best using a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

There are many methods of preparing pollen grains for SEM examination. Some

good grain quality. It has resisted insect and disease problems in Bihar, including bacterial blight, tungro, and brown plant-hopper. Its short duration makes it useful for multicropping in irrigated systems. Those traits encourage IR36 adoption for general cultivation in Bihar. □

Table 2. Performance of IR36 in adaptive research farms, 1981 wet season.

Location	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	IR36	CR44-35 (check)
Araria	3.8	3.6
Barbat	2.7	2.0
Nagri	4.2	3.7
Simdega	3.7	3.4

^a Percentage increase over the check is 15.1.

Table 3. Performance of IR36 in Bihar in 1979 and 1982 dry season.

Test entry	Yield (t/ha) at	
	Patna	Pusa
	1979	
IR36	4.9	3.9
CR44-35 (check)	3.7	3.0
CD at 5%	ns	1.1
	1982	
IR36	5.6	2.4
Cauvery (check)	5.4	3.5
CD at 5%.	7.6	8.8

scientists indicate that a fresh pollen grain can be observed directly; others write that acetolysis is necessary. We studied sample preparation for SEM as follows, using pollen grains from six *Oryza* species.

Pollen collection and preservation

- A1. Anthers and pollen grains were air-dried.
- A2. Anthers and pollen grains were fixed in Carnoy's fluid for 2-3 hours, and transferred to 70% ethanol.
- A3. Samples were fixed in 4% glutaraldehyde for 16 hours (0-4°C), washed with phosphate buffer 1 or 2 times, stored in the same solution, and placed in vials and kept in the refrigerator.

Methods of cleaning or dehydrating pollen grains after treatment A

- B1. Sample was placed in acetolysis mixture (9 parts acetic anhydride and 1 part sulfuric acid) and heated in a 100°C water bath for about 1 minute, then washed in distilled water 3-4 times and air-dried;
- B2. Sample was washed with glacial acetic acid, then was washed 3 times with distilled water and air-dried.
- B3. Sample was dehydrated serially using different ethanol concentrations.
- B4. Untreated pollen grains were spread on double stick tape directly from the anthers.

Determining necessity for critical point drying after treatment B

- C1. Critical point dryer was not used.
- C2. Critical point dryer was used.

All the methods tried for pollen collection and preservation can be used depending on convenience. If B1 is used to clean specimens, critical point drying to maintain the shape of the pollen grain is not necessary. Samples did not collapse under the SEM even at 12.5 or higher KV. The 2000X to 10000X photomicrographs showed the surface sculpture clearly (Fig. 1), but all the opercula were lost.

B3 can be used after A2 or A4, but it must be followed by critical point drying. The pollen grains, including opercula, can be observed with clear surface sculpture at 7000X (Fig. 2). When magnified 10000X, their image is less clear than that of acetolyzed samples (B1). Perhaps the matrix was not removed and affected clarity. B3 granules seem smaller and shallower than those of B1. To compare surface textures of pollen grains, however, 4500X is sufficient magnification.

Pollen grains from B2 and B4, if not followed by critical point drying, collapsed and cracked easily when exposed to the vacuum and the electron beam of the SEM except at 1000X for a very short time, where the texture of the exine cannot be seen clearly.

Acetolysis with 2000 to 4500X magnification is best for comparing surface structure of different *Oryza* pollen grains.

□

1. Pollen grain of *Oryza barthii* showing surface texture (7000 X). Samples were acetolyzed without critical point drying.

2. Pollen grain of *Oryza longistaminata* showing intact operculum after glutaraldehyde fixation and serial dehydration in ethanol (7000 X). Critical point drying was used.